

Audit Committee and Audit Delay of Listed Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of audit committee on Audit Delay of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The ex-post facto research design was employed in the study. Secondary data was collected from annual reports and accounts of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The population of the study is twenty One (21) and the sample size is fifteen (15) for a period 10 years (2012-2021). Six (6) firms were flitter out due the technical suspension by NGX during the period of this study. The study employed a census sample technique. Panel corrected standard errors (PCSEs) model was employed as technique of data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that the audit committee size (ACS) has a negative and significant effect on Audit Delay (AD). Also, the Audit Committee Financial Expertise (ACFE) revealed a positive and insignificant effect on Audit Delay (AD). The study recommended that the management of the firms should continue to sustain the size or numbers of the committee in their respective audit committee since the committee size have been empirically proven to have significantly reduced the time frame of reporting.

Keywords: audit committee, audit delay, consumer goods firm, listed firms, Nigeria

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1. Introduction

The objective of financial reporting is to provide accounting information to assist users of financial statements to assess the amount, timing and uncertainty of entity's future cash inflow and outflow, so as to make informed decision. For accounting information to be decision useful to shareholders and potential investors, The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) requires that the financial report must possess certain fundamental and enhancing qualities. One of the keys qualities is timeliness of information. According to Adewale and Sarah (2019) if financial information is not available when it is due, but rather is made available so late that it is no longer useful for future action, then it is operationally irrelevant.

Timeliness of corporate accounting information is refers as the number of days from the date of financial year-end to the date the external auditor signs the audit report and published it to the public (Aifuwa et al., 2020). Timeliness is one of the fundamental qualitative characteristics of financial reporting which determine the quality of information in a company financial statement (Odjaremu & Jeroh, 2019). This suggests that financial information should be timely prepared to meet user needs such that companies do not risk losing their potential of influencing the decisions of such users. Also, Information potentially loses relevance with age, and extended delays in the availability of financial information render the accounting information less useful for economic decision (Maranjory & Tajani, 2022).

Disclosure and presentation of financial reports is one key factors of good corporate governance. The timeliness of financial reporting problems can be solved by implementing good corporate governance through the establishment of an audit committee (Alshrife, Subekti & Widya, 2016). It is therefore argued that audit committees have a fundamental role in a company to improve upon the quality of financial report through prompt and timely reporting the information. According to the Companies and Allied Matters Act (1990, as amended in 2020), audit committee is one of the important operating committees of board of directors of a company' that is responsible with supervisory role, monitoring and overseeing financial reporting process and disclosure of financial information to the public for decision making. Abu et al. (2018) provide empirical evidence on linking the effectiveness of audit committees to the characteristics of the committee of a company. Prior empirical research such as the studies of Nazari et al. (2020) Zaitul and Ilona (2018), Eyenubo et al. (2017) state the characteristics of audit committee as the audit committee size, independence, committee diligence, gender diversity, expertise of the committee members.

The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) which is the regulatory agency of Nigeria stock market sets March 31 for every listed firm to submit its audited financial reports ended on December 31 in the previous year. Other Nigerian regulators such as the Investment and Security Act and Insurance Act require a financial statement to be made available on or before 90 and 180 days respectively. However, research has shown that timely financial reports add value to the content of the information and increase the value of the company. This is therefore necessary to examine audit committee attributes that influence Audit Delay and how the institutional shareholdings of the company influence the effectiveness of committee attributes. Also, the most essential justification of the study is due to the limitation of use of moderating variable to establish the interaction between institutional shareholdings and audit committee characteristics on Audit Delay.

Despite the fact that audit committee attributes exists in corporate governance report of companies, yet, it is relatively scanty when accessing its influence on the timeliness of financial report in consumable sector. Most researchers focuses their studies on the quantitative factors of financial reporting such as studies of Bala et al., (2018), Mohammad and Ahmed, (2017), Umar et al., (2016)

adapting different models like Accruals model, Discretionary accruals model, Modified-jones model. This study will therefore focus on the qualitative factors of financial reporting such as the audit delay of financial reporting and to also further access how the audit committee attributes of board influence the timeliness of financial reporting to the public. Furthermore, past studies have considered the relationship between audit committee attributes and Audit Delay with mixed and divergent findings, for instance the study of Maranjory and Tajani (2022), Nazari et al. (2020), Aifuwa et al., (2020), Chukwu and Nwabochi (2019), Puasa et al., (2019), Odjaremu and Jeroh, (2019), Abu et al., (2018), Zaitul and Ilona (2018), Tinumbia et al., (2018), Eyenubo et al., (2017), Alshrifé et al., (2016), Emeh and Ebimobowei, (2013), Ika and Ghazali, (2012), however, none of this studies considered moderating variable in their study to the best of the researcher knowledge of which this study consider by introducing institutional shareholdings as a moderator. Therefore, the question shall be raised whether audit committee attributes such as Audit committee size, and Audit committee financial expertise influence audit delay. Hence, the main objective of this study is to examine the effect of audit committee and audit delay of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

The specific research objectives shall be as follows:

- i. To examine the influence of audit committee size on Audit Delay of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria.
- ii. To ascertain the influence of audit committee financial expertise on Audit Delay of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria.
- iii. To assess the influence of Audit Delay of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria.

The following hypotheses are stated and tested in null form;

- i. Audit committee size has no significant influence on Audit Delay of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria
- ii. Audit committee financial expertise has no significant influence on Audit Delay of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria
- iii. Audit delay has no significant influence on financial reporting of listed consumer good firms in Nigeria

2. Literature Review

Audit delay (also known as timeliness) is a fundamental component of general-purpose financial reporting. Timeliness is an essential feature of financial reporting to agents, allowing them to make informed decisions about the entity. Maranjory and Tajani (2022) identify the causes of Audit Delay for two reasons: firstly, it improves the understanding of the financial reporting process; secondly, Audit Delay is directly related to timely earnings announcements. Audit Delay as the period between a company's accounting year end and the publication of the financial report to the users of accounting information (Okechukwu et al., 2021). likewise, Rahmansyah et al. (2021) documented that Audit Delay as the ability of a company to meet the submission deadlines of financial statement set by law such as Nigerian Exchange Group and Security Exchange Commission.

Audit committee is responsible for ensuring firm compliance with regulations related to the firm. firms that comply with regulations will support the creation of good financial statements that are free of errors and injustices so that it will shorten the audit report lag (Juwita et al., 2020). Audit committee is an important mechanism for effective governance, as it is responsible for assessing the efficiency and adequacy of internal control systems, overseeing and controlling the financial reporting process, and acting as an external auditor (Abdulrahman et al., 2021). The Audit

committee must also have non-executive directors, the majority of whom must be independent. Furthermore, the AC must have at least three members, with at least one of them having accounting/finance expertise.

The CAMA 2004 provides that audit committee size should not exceed six. Chukwu and Nwabochi (2019) stated that audit committee size is important because it signals the importance attached to the committee. Further noted that a large audit committee member is blessed with different viewpoints in deliberating on financial reporting issues. Nazari et al. (2020) describe audit committee's financial expertise describes the expert skills or knowledge in accounting and finance possessed by the members of the audit committee of a company. Hashim and Rahman (2011) demonstrate that experience in accounting or auditing is essential for the audit committee member to understand and address the problematic issue in the company's financial reporting system. Odjaremu and Jeroh (2019) reported that audit committee with financial knowledge understood the importance of producing timely financial statements for the public.

Afenya et al. (2022) assess the impact of audit committee financial expertise on the financial report timeliness of Ghanaian publicly traded companies. Secondary data was extracted from the financial statements of companies registered on the Ghana stock exchange from the period of 2008 to 2019. The population of the study is 38 companies and the sample size is 25 listed companies traded on the Ghanaian stock market. The study used a multivariate ordinary least square regression. The study findings found that audit committee size and audit committee financial expertise has a significant negative impact on financial report timeliness.

Maranjory and Tajani (2022) examine the effect of audit committee financial expertise on the financial reporting of firms listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE). A unique data for a period of 5-years between 2016 and 2020 through content analysis of the financial statements. A multivariate linear regression model with panel data was used for the data analysis with the support of EViews 8 software. Hausman test is used to select between fixed and random effects models and the test found random effect suitable for the study. The findings of the study revealed that audit committee financial expertise has a negative and significant effect on financial report timeliness, while audit committee size revealed a negative and insignificant effect on financial report timeliness.

Nouraldeen et al. (2021) investigate the determinants of financial report timeliness in developing countries like Lebanon, the Middle East countries by focusing on the Lebanese context. The study is carried out depending on a sample of Lebanese commercial banks operating in Lebanon, covering the period from 2012 to 2017. The study used multiple regression analysis to analysis the extracted data. Findings from the research results show that audit committee size has a negative and no insignificant effect on financial report timeliness. While audit committee size revealed a negative and insignificant effect on financial report timeliness.

Mobarak et al. (2021) examine the effect of audit committee size on financial report timeliness of non-financial Saudi-listed companies between the period of 2015 and 2018. Form the 125 listed companies, a sample of 99 companies from 16 sectors was selected due to incomplete or ambiguous data. Poisson regression model was used to analysis the extracted panel data. The findings of the study established that audit committee size has a positive and insignificant effect on financial report timeliness. While the audit committee size revealed a positive and insignificant effect on financial report timeliness.

Ovbiebo (2021) assesses the effect of audit committee size on financial report timeliness (audit report lag) among Nigeria-listed insurance companies. Twenty (20) quoted insurance companies in the Nigeria Stock Exchange as of 31st December 2020 and the sample of five (5) listed Insurance

companies were obtained from their respective annual reports covering the period 2016 to 2020. A convenient sampling technique was used in the study. A secondary source of panel data was collected and content analysis was employed in the study. The panel Least Square (PLS) regression estimation techniques were used to analyse the data. The study found that audit committee size (ACS) has an insignificant positive effect on financial report timeliness (audit report lag) and the audit committee financial expertise revealed a significant negative effect on financial report timeliness.

Ezat et al. (2021) investigate the impact of audit committee size on audit reports Saudi listed non-financial firms in 2018 of 126 firm-year observations. The study data was collected from the annual reports of listed firms that were from 16 sectors. The financial companies and banks were excluded due to their different characteristics; also, three firms with missing data are excluded. The OLS regression model was used to analysis the data. Findings of the study revealed that audit committee size has an insignificant and negative effect on financial report timeliness (audit report lag). Audit committee financial expertise revealed a significant negative effect on financial report timeliness.

3. Methodology

The study employed ex-post facto design. The data were source through the annual report and accounts of the consumer good firms from the year 2012 to 2021. Panel corrected standard errors analysis was be adopted for the study. Post estimation tests such as Multicollinearity, Heteroskedasticity, was used to ensure the fitness of the selected model. Population of the study is twenty-one (21) listed consumer good firms and sample size is fifteen (15). Census sample technique was adopted for the study. As presented in Table 1

The model encapsulates the contribution of audit committee characteristics on Audit Delay;

$$AD_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 ACS_{it} + \beta_2 ACFE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Model on introduction of Moderation variable of institutional ownership on the interaction between the audit committee attributes on Audit Delay

$$AD_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 ACS_{it} + \beta_2 ACFE_{it} + \beta_3 ACS_{it} + \beta_4 ACFE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots (ii)$$

Whereas:

AD= Audit Delay is measure by the Number of days from date of financial year-end (FYED) to the date of auditor sign the audit report (ARD). ACS= Total Number of Audit Committee Member, ACFE= Percentage of Financial Expertise of Audit Committee on the audit committee. i= number bank observation, 1- -20, t= the index of time periods, ϵ =is the error component for company, β_0 = Intercept of the model “Constant”, $\beta = 1, 2 \dots$ are parameters to be estimate

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the analysis conducted on the data collected from the annual report and report and account of the companies under study. The descriptive statistics, diagnostic test and PCSEs model are presented in the study.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1

Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
AD	150	85.56667	31.10308	34	214
ACS	150	5.766667	0.6991526	2	6
ACFE	150	0.1007913	0.1001989	0	0.3333

Sources: Stata 14 Result Output

The descriptive statistics on Table 1 revealed that Audit Delay (AD) has a mean of 85.57, this implies the average days between the financial year-end and submission of the signed audited report was 85 days. By implication, in Nigeria most audited annual reports for firms listed on the Stock Exchange are ready by the third month each financial year. A standard deviation of 31.10, with a minimum and maximum of 34 and 214 respectively, the standard deviation of 31.10 signifies no much variation in (AD) of the companies within the period under study. The average mean number of the audit committee size is 5.7 (6 members) with a minimum 2 and a maximum of 6 committee members. Similarly, the audit committee financial expert (ACFE) had a mean value of 0.10, with minimum and maximum of 0 and 0.33. This implies that at least 33% of members in the committee have sound accounting and financial knowledge.

This section employed an PCSEs Regression model show the effect of audit committee attributes on Audit Delay. The result in table 2 revealed that model has a presence of Heteroskedasticity in the panel as indicated by the Breuch Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity Chi2 of 5.68 with p-value of 0.0172. In additions, the model also revealed that there is absence of the perfect multicollinearity among the explanatory or independent variables of the study, as shown by the mean VIF of 1.19. Furthermore, the table revealed that the result of R² of 8% signifies that total variation in the Audit Delay (AD) is caused by audit committee size, and audit committee financial expertise, in the study. Also, the table 2 shows that the model is fitted for the study due to the F-Statistic P-value of 0.0010, which is statistically significant at 1% level of significance. The fixed effect and random effect model was run to determine the best fitted model and hausman test result show chi2 value of 33.24 and Prob>chi2 = 0.0000 which indicate that fixed effect model is the best, however, panel corrected standard errors (PCSEs) model was adopted in order to correct for the presence of Heteroskedasticity in the model.

Table 2

Summary of PCSEs Regression Model

Variables	Coefficient value	P-value
ACS	9.2543	0.030
ACFE	14.0494	0.476
FIRM SIZE	-5.2143	0.001
SALES GROWTH	14.4194	0.078
Constant	156.41	0.000
Hetest	5.68	0.0172
Mean VIF		1.19
R ²		0.0840
F-Statistics		0.0010

Sources: Output generated using STATA 13 @ 5% level of significant

Testing of Hypotheses

H0: Audit Committee Size has no significant effect on Audit Delay

From the multiple regression model, the study revealed a beta coefficient (β) of 9.2543 and $p < 0.030$. The null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that audit committee size (ACS) has significant positive effect on Audit Delay (AD) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria exchange group. This means a 1% increase in audit committee size (ACS), will lead to an significant increase in the audit delay of the study firm by 9.2%. The result suggested that the listed consumer goods firms should reduce the number of the audit committee. Therefore, six member of audit committee in a company gives more opportunity for conflicts to arise among members and hinder the auditing process, thereby creating a greater audit report lag. Therefore, this outcome is in tandem with previous findings of (Al-qublani et al.,2020), revealed that ACS has a positive

significance effect on AD, but contradict the study of Abu et al. (2018) revealed an insignificant effect on AD.

H0₂: Audit Committee Financial Expertise has no significant effect on Audit Delay

Using the PCSEs regression model revealed the beta coefficient (β) of 14.0494 and $\rho < 0.476$. The null hypothesis fails to be rejected and it was concluded that audit committee financial expertise (ACFE) has a positive and insignificant effect on Audit Delay (AD) of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria exchange group. Therefore, the higher the proportion of audit committee financial expertise (ACFE) by 1%, may not adequately increase the Audit Delay (AD) by about 15%. The means that the (ACFE) in the committee may reduce delay of Audit Delay and this may be attributed to due process of ACFE. A committee that wants prudence, transparency and accountability and due diligence may sometime reduce delay in reporting. Furthermore, financial experts on audit committee number may reduce incident of fraud. Therefore, this outcome is in tandem with previous findings of Mobarak et al. (2021), but contradict the findings of Al-qublani et al. (2020).

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of audit committee attributes on audit delay of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings the study concludes that audit committee size has a significant positive influence on Audit Delay of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The results of this study indicate that the existence of an audit committee can shorten the timeliness of financial reporting. The better quality of the audit committee causes the Audit Delay to be lower. Therefore, the study recommend that management of the listed consumer goods firms should review the size or numbers of the committee in their respective audit committee since the size has empirically proven to have significantly increase audit delay.

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APPENDIX

Table 1

Population of the Study

S/N	Consumer Goods Firm	Period of Study	Observation
1.	Cadbury Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
2.	Champion Breweries Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
3.	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
4.	DN Tyre & Rubber Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
5.	Flour Mills Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
6.	Golden Guinea Breweries Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
7.	Guinness Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
8.	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
9.	International Breweries Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
10.	MCNICHOLS Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
11.	Multi-Trex Integrated Foods Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
12.	Nigeria Flour Mills Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
13.	NASCON Allied Industries Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
14.	Nestle Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
15.	Nigerian Breweries Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
16.	Nigerian Enamel Ware Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
17.	PZ Cussons Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
18.	Unilever Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
19.	Union DICON Salt Plc.	2012 – 2021	10
20.	BUA Foods Plc	2012 – 2021	10
21.	Vita Form Nigeria Plc.	2012 – 2021	10

Sources: Nigerian Exchange Group Website, 2021